

Framing the Potential Benefits of Traditional Chinese Exercises for the Management of Patients with Knee Osteoarthritis – A Narrative Review.

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Abstract: Background: Knee osteoarthritis (KOA) is a prevalent chronic degenerative joint disease, causing significant pain and functional limitations, impacting quality of life. Traditional Chinese Exercises (TCEs) are increasingly explored as complementary therapies. This narrative review aims to frame the potential benefits of TCEs for KOA management.

Methods: Database search was conducted to find relevant studies on the topic and according to the study's objectives. Guidelines and relevant studies were reviewed to assess the impact of TCEs on physical function, pain, and psychological well-being.

Results: TCEs have demonstrated significant benefits in improving balance, flexibility, and muscle strength, crucial for KOA management. Tai Chi has been shown to reduce pain and improve physical function, self-efficacy, depression, and health-related quality of life. Qigong has also been associated with pain reduction, enhanced psychological well-being, improved knee joint proprioception, postural stability, and reduced stiffness and functional impairments. TCEs offer a holistic approach by integrating physical, mental, and emotional benefits, aligning with recommendations from organizations like the American College of Rheumatology (ACR).

Conclusions: TCEs represent a valuable complementary therapy for KOA, offering a holistic and non-pharmacological approach to pain management and improved quality of life. Integrating these practices into mainstream clinical settings could empower patients to actively manage their KOA symptoms. Further high-quality randomized controlled trials are needed to standardize protocols and optimize the integration of TCEs within Western healthcare systems.

Keywords: Knee Osteoarthritis; Traditional Chinese Exercises; Tai Chi; Qigong; Pain Management; Complementary Therapy.

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1. Background

Osteoarthritis (OA) is a chronic disorder characteristic of aging, and it is the most common chronic joint disease, lacking effective resources to delay its progression. It can manifest in joints of any size, with the knee being the most affected joint in men and women over 60 years old¹. Globally, OA is estimated to affect about 7.6% of the population, particularly prevalent in knee and hip joints, with these numbers expected to rise sharply by 2050². In the systematic analysis of the Global Burden of Disease published in 2020³, OA affects approximately 527.81 million people worldwide, with the knee accounting for 60.6% of the OA burden^{3,4}. In Portugal, according to the Instituto Português de Reumatologia (IPR), OA is a significant public health problem, representing the most common rheumatic disease and the leading cause of chronic pain. It accounts for about

30–40% of outpatient rheumatology consultations⁵. The Liga Portuguesa Contra as Doenças Reumáticas (LPCDR) confirms these findings and adds that knee OA affects 12.4% of the Portuguese population, followed by hip OA with 8.7% and hand OA with 2.9% prevalence⁶.

The knee joint comprises the distal end of the femur, the proximal end of the tibia, the patella, cartilage (meniscus and articular cartilage), ligaments, the infrapatellar fat pad (IFP), and the synovial membrane. The synovial membrane produces synovial fluid, which nourishes and lubricates the cartilage. Cartilage, such as that covering the femur and tibia, is composed of 70% water, extracellular matrix components—primarily type II collagen and proteoglycans like aggrecan—and chondrocytes. These cells detect mechanical stress and changes in the extracellular matrix, including inflammatory mediators. In response to mechanical or inflammatory stimulation, there is an increase in the activity of aggrecanase, collagenase, and other metalloproteinases, leading to cartilage degradation, which becomes irreversible when collagen network integrity is compromised. The knee joint is subject to significant mechanical stress, contributing to an increased risk of OA development⁷.

In OA, changes are not limited to the gradual disappearance of cartilage associated with chondrocyte loss and extracellular matrix modification; subchondral bone remodeling also occurs. The subchondral bone contains blood vessels within vascular channels that house osteoblasts and sensory nerves, facilitating biochemical communication between bone and cartilage. Inflammatory mediators produced by chondrocytes in response to various stimuli act as paracrine factors, initiating a vicious cycle of cartilage degradation, reaching the synovial fluid, and triggering joint inflammation. This damages the cartilage and induces changes in adjacent joint tissues⁷. The inflammatory mediators involved in OA, upon reaching the sensory nerve endings in vascular channels, elicit nociceptive perception, manifesting as tibiofemoral pain⁸. The IFP and synovial membrane can be considered a morpho-functional unit due to their close contact, as the adipose tissue in the IFP secretes adipokines that influence the joint. Similarly, knee joint inflammation may be associated with increased inflammation and fibrotic changes in the IFP^{9,10}.

Cartilage is a highly specialized connective tissue, and its damage is the hallmark of OA. The main risk factors for OA include aging, female gender, overweight/obesity, metabolic syndrome, joint trauma, genetic predisposition, and occupational load^{11,12}. Preventing OA involves reducing risks from childhood through public health campaigns, focusing on high-risk groups such as athletes. Addressing both internal risk factors (e.g., obesity and genetics) and external ones (e.g., joint injuries) is crucial, with priority given to obesity and sports injuries, particularly at specific life stages¹³. Preventing OA is challenging as it incurs costs and interferes with cultural and dietary habits. Strengthening exercises reduce joint injuries but have low adherence due to a lack of motivation, emphasizing the importance of education about OA's consequences on quality of life and well-being as an incentive for lifestyle changes¹².

1.2. Knee Osteoarthritis management

Knee Osteoarthritis (KOA) is incurable, therefore therapeutic goals include pain control, increased mobility, and improved well-being¹⁴. KOA treatment must integrate symptoms affecting physical conditions, such as pain and functional limitations, with psychological factors, including anxiety, depression, and sleep pattern disruptions. The therapeutic plan for KOA may involve various interventions: surgical, pharmacological, psychosocial, and those promoting general well-being (e.g., stress reduction, mood improvement, sleep regulation, weight control, and enhanced physical condition). These may be implemented individually, sequentially, or in combination. Determining the best KOA treatment requires considering the patient's overall health status, including comorbidities (e.g., hypertension, cardiovascular disease, heart failure, digestive bleeding risk, chronic kidney disease), as well as the patient's beliefs and preferences¹⁵. KOA treatment should

begin with non-surgical interventions, potentially progressing to surgical treatments if pharmacological and non-pharmacological therapies prove clinically ineffective¹⁴.

Weight loss, improved motor control, and low-impact exercise are the primary goals of conservative KOA treatment, improving physical fitness, quality of life, and reducing OA-associated pain^{14,16}. Weight control is particularly important, as there is a positive correlation between weight loss and symptom improvement or functionality in OA patients. A reduction of $\geq 5\%$ in body weight is associated with clinical improvement, with clinical benefits increasing with reductions of 5–10%, 10–20%, and $>20\%$ in body weight. The effectiveness of weight loss in treating OA symptoms is enhanced by the concurrent implementation of an exercise program¹⁷.

Conventional non-surgical or conservative KOA treatments

Conventional non-surgical or conservative KOA treatment includes physiotherapy and pharmacological therapies. Physiotherapy encompasses therapeutic exercises aimed at increasing muscle strength and endurance, providing greater stability, reducing pain and inflammation¹⁸, and improving joint and muscle range of motion¹⁵. Supervised KOA treatment by a physiotherapist is crucial for adherence, as these professionals assist with exercises, use orthopaedic materials, and perform thermal therapies, among other interventions¹⁵. Therapeutic exercises include walking, stationary biking, water aerobics, isokinetic weight machines, resistance bands, isometric exercises, and balance exercises¹⁵. KOA patients experiencing pain, stiffness, and swelling require pharmacological treatment, whether topical, injectable, or oral. All medication therapy aims solely to treat symptoms, aiding in patient mobility control¹⁴. Pharmacological treatment can be classified into two major groups: fast-acting medications and slow-acting medications, including structure-modifying drugs. Medication therapy should be complemented by non-pharmacological therapies, such as physical exercise¹⁶. Nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) aim to control inflammation and provide analgesia for KOA patients. Topical formulations are preferred over oral ones, as they present fewer side effects in patients with multiple comorbidities. However, when topical formulations do not control pain, oral formulations may be considered for moderate to severe pain under medical evaluation. NSAIDs prescriptions should always be tailored to the patient, with treatment monitored to avoid adverse effects, and the lowest effective dose should be used for the shortest necessary duration. For patients in whom NSAIDs are contraindicated, glucocorticoid injections offer highly effective short-term KOA treatment. Similarly, tramadol or other opioids are alternative treatments to NSAIDs. Disease-modifying anti-rheumatic drugs, such as methotrexate, are recommended for KOA patients, helping control disease symptoms¹⁵. Biological therapy implemented intra-articularly, using FDA and EMA approved drugs, is another option for KOA treatment. Hyaluronic acid, a naturally occurring substance in synovial fluid, contributes to pain relief, stimulates synovial fluid production, and promotes cushioning and lubrication of joint surfaces. This therapy is increasingly used as it seeks to delay surgical intervention, being administered in a concentrated dosage directly into the affected joint with minimal side effect risk. Other therapies, such as intra-articular injections of platelet-rich plasma, stem cells, dextrose prolotherapy, and genicular nerve block, are also employed as adjuncts in KOA treatment, aiming to reduce pain, swelling, and improve joint function¹⁴. Orthopedic devices and materials, such as lateral wedge insoles, canes, and knee braces, are recommended for KOA patients^{14,15}. The lateral wedge insole contributes to pain relief and improves the functional state of the joint¹⁴. The use of canes is recommended for KOA patients when the disease compromises walking, joint stability, or causes pain. Tibiofemoral knee braces are recommended for KOA patients if the disease significantly impairs joint mobility and stability, and the patient can tolerate the discomfort and load associated with the orthosis¹⁵.

Surgical KOA treatments

Patients with KOA who experience significantly compromised quality of life and for whom conservative treatment fails to alleviate pain or improve joint movement should be considered candidates for surgical treatment. Various types of surgery, such as arthroscopy, arthroplasty, and osteotomy, aim to improve the quality of life for OA patients. It is important to note that different techniques have limitations and risks. For example, arthroscopic surgery may not be more effective than conservative treatments such as physiotherapy. Knee arthroplasty (total or partial replacement) is recommended for advanced KOA cases, especially in elderly patients, as it effectively alleviates pain and improves joint function, though it may have significant side effects. Osteotomy is another surgical option to reduce the need for joint replacement in younger KOA patients. This procedure redistributes the load to the healthy compartment of the knee, preserving its function. It is most effective in early-stage KOA patients under 50 years of age with partially preserved cartilage. However, the success of the procedure may be influenced by factors such as the patient's weight¹⁴.

Complementary therapies for KOA

Conservative therapeutic approaches for KOA patients extend beyond conventional treatment. It is also included in a broad and diverse set of treatments that can be applied alternatively or complementarily with Western Medicine (WM). Mud therapy is a safe and cost-effective approach to treating KOA, promoting recovery through the heat and minerals present in the mud, alleviating pain, and improving function. The local application of mud can be an effective complementary therapy for OA treatment, offering pain relief and additional benefits to the patient's well-being¹⁹. According to the recommendations issued in 2019 by the American College of Rheumatology/Arthritis Foundation for the Management of Osteoarthritis of the Hand, Hip, and Knee, participation in self-efficacy and self-management programs may help KOA patients. These programs use a multidisciplinary format with the goals of helping patients set goals, solve problems, encourage positive thinking, educate them about the disease and medication side effects, provide joint protection measures, and address fitness and exercise approaches¹⁵. Cognitive-behavioral therapy (CBT) is indicated for chronic pain conditions, benefiting KOA patients by relieving pain, improving quality of life, mitigating negative mood states, alleviating fatigue, enhancing functional capacity, and reducing disability^{20,21}. Yoga is a mind-body practice rooted in ancient Indian philosophy and typically combines physical postures, breathing techniques, and meditation or relaxation. Although much less studied than Tai Chi, Yoga can be helpful in KOA through a similar combination of physical and psychosocial factors¹⁵.

While WM focuses on symptom management through pharmacologic and surgical interventions, Traditional Chinese Medicine (TCM) emphasizes holistic, energy-based approaches, encompassing acupuncture, moxibustion, herbal medicine, and massage. TCM has been used for millennia in China to treat various pathological conditions, especially chronic pain²². It is frequently applied in KOA treatment²², providing symptom relief with minimal adverse reactions and high applicability for patients with comorbidities²³. According to the TCM Diagnostic and Treatment Guide for Knee Osteoarthritis (2020), KOA can be classified into five types: Qi stagnation and blood stasis, damp-heat obstruction, cold-damp obstruction, liver and kidney deficiency, and Qi and blood weakness²⁴. In TCM theory, KOA is considered a form of "bone obstruction" or "Bi disease," where "evil spirits" penetrate the bone marrow, exacerbating symptoms. TCM aims to restore joint functions, reduce pain, and improve mobility to treat KOA effectively²⁵. Chinese herbal medicine plays a significant role in KOA treatment, with several plants demonstrating recognized therapeutic benefits in both TCM and WM. Commonly used plants include *Dipsacus asper* Wall. ex-Henry, *Chaenomeles sinensis* (Thouin) Koehne, *Rhizoma Polygoni Cuspidati*, *Achyranthis Bidentatae Radix*, *Eucommia ulmoides* Oliv., *Paeonia*

Radix Alba, Angelica sinensis, and Curcuma longa L²³. Herbal formulas combining various plants are preferred over isolated use, providing more balanced and effective actions while reducing toxicity associated with certain substances²³. Widely used compounds include Yougui Wan, Duhuo Jisheng Decoction, and Simiao Wan²³. Registered Chinese medicines for KOA treatment include Wangbi tablets, Xianling Gubao capsules, Duhuo Jisheng tablets, Jintiange capsules, and Longbie capsules, among others. These medicines have shown remarkable effects in treating KOA²³. Topical application of Chinese herbal pastes, moxibustion, and heat on the affected area have significant therapeutic effects, as they help warm the meridians, disperse pernicious Qi, promote blood circulation, cellular metabolism, lymphatic drainage, and alleviate inflammation²³. Acupuncture, a widely used TCM technique globally, is recognized as an effective and safe therapy for pain relief, suitable for various types of musculoskeletal pain, including pain and functional recovery in KOA patients^{26–29}. It may offer greater efficacy and fewer adverse reactions compared to WM treatments^{30,31}. TCM also includes exercises applicable for both prevention and treatment: TCEs, the most studied of which is Tai Chi. Tai Chi offers similar benefits to physiotherapy in pain relief and improved physical function, with the added advantages of reducing depression symptoms and improving quality of life. TCEs have similar benefits to physical therapies, being low-to-moderate intensity and focusing on coordinating breathing and body movement³². TCEs have evolved over thousands of years into a distinctive system that integrates physical movement, meditative stillness, and philosophical principles to promote health and prevent disease. Guided by concepts such as the Yin-Yang doctrine, the Five Elements theory, and the meridian Zang Fu organ framework, TCEs aims to regulate Qi and blood, unblock energy pathways, and enhance physical and mental well-being. These practices harmonize gentle movements with muscle stretching, controlled breathing, and mental focus, forming a holistic approach that has gained global recognition^{33–35}. Numerous studies underscore the benefits of TCEs for a wide range of medical conditions, including cardiovascular, respiratory, musculoskeletal, and endocrine disorders, as well as balance issues. Renowned organizations like the Osteoarthritis Research Society International (OARSI) and the American College of Rheumatology (ACR) endorse these exercises as safe and effective non-pharmacological interventions. Among the most popular forms of TCEs are Tai Chi, Qigong, Baduanjin, Yijinjing, and Wuqinxi³⁶.

Tai Chi: This traditional martial art is characterized by slow, controlled movements combined with deep breathing, often described as "meditation in motion." Tai Chi enhances physical health, mental clarity, and spiritual balance through fluid postures requiring focus and control. Studies demonstrate its effectiveness in improving mindfulness, reducing anxiety, and increasing pain tolerance³³.

Qigong: Combining movement, breath control, and meditation, Qigong aims to cultivate and balance qi. It is particularly suitable for older adults with chronic conditions, improving cardiovascular health, immune function, and mental clarity. Variants like the "White Ball" system provide clinical benefits in just 5–6 minutes of practice daily, as observed through studies using infrared thermography^{37–39}.

Baduanjin: Known as the "Eight Pieces of Brocade," this form of Qigong comprises eight movements designed to enhance flexibility, strength, and qi flow. Research supports its role in improving cognitive function and physiological parameters in various clinical populations^{34,36}.

Yijinjing: This practice combines dynamic movements with breath control to strengthen muscles and tendons, promoting energy circulation and physical resilience. It also restores balance between the body and mind³⁴.

Wuqinxi: Also known as the "Five Animal Frolics," this exercise mimics the movements of animals such as the tiger, deer, and bird. Designed by the renowned physician Hua Tuo, it improves flexibility, strength, and energy circulation. A simplified version is widely practiced in modern China³⁷.

2. Health Benefits of TCEs

TCE serves as a complementary therapy to enhance blood circulation, regulate organ functions, and activate muscles and tendons through coordinated movements, breathing, and meditation^{33,34,36,39,40}.

Physical benefits: Tai Chi improves balance, flexibility, and muscle strength, offering effective interventions for older adults and individuals with chronic conditions. Its integration of movement and breath helps reduce joint strain and enhances lower limb strength⁴⁰. **Mental and emotional benefits:** practices like Qigong and Tai Chi induce relaxation and mental clarity, reducing stress and anxiety while promoting emotional resilience. Studies indicate these exercises foster natural pain relief by enhancing circulation and releasing endorphins³⁶. **Integration of movement and breath:** exercises such as Yijinjing and Baduanjin emphasize the synchronization of physical movement with controlled breathing, improving physiological functions and restoring energy balance. Baduanjin has been particularly effective in addressing psychological and physiological challenges, such as chronic fatigue syndrome and Parkinson's disease³⁷.

2.1. Effects of TCEs on Musculoskeletal Disorders

TCE has demonstrated significant benefits in improving balance, flexibility, and muscle strength, making it highly effective for individuals with musculoskeletal conditions^{33,35}. **Joint health:** studies reveal improvements in knee joint function and reduced inflammatory markers, offering natural pain relief and improved mobility^{33,35}. **Lubrication and flexibility:** the low-impact movements inherent to these exercises stimulate joint lubrication, reduce stiffness, and enhance physical endurance, providing long-term benefits for joint health^{33,35}.

2.2. Benefits of TCE in Osteoarthritis

TCEs, including Tai Chi, Qigong, Baduanjin, Yijinjing, and Wuqinxi, have been increasingly recognized for its therapeutic potential in addressing musculoskeletal disorders^{34,35,37}. **Evidence-based benefits:** high-quality randomized controlled trials have shown that TCEs significantly reduces pain, improves physical function, and alleviates inflammation in individuals with KOA. Tai Chi is recommended by the ACR guidelines since 2019 and exemplifies the global application of these practices³⁴. Moreover, Tai Chi is directly associated to improvements in pain⁴¹⁻⁴³, physical function, self-efficacy, depression, and health-related quality of life⁴³ in OA patients. On the other hand, Qigong also is associated with improvements in pain^{44,45}, psychological well-being (reduced stress, anxiety, depression, and mood disturbance), as well as improvements in knee joint proprioception and postural stability, reduction of stiffness and functional impairments⁴⁵ in KOA patients.

TCEs may serve the so needed holistic approach by combining physical, mental, and emotional benefits, offering a comprehensive approach to managing KOA. This holistic strategy not only enhances patients' quality of life but also underscores the value of non-pharmacological interventions in modern healthcare³⁶.

3. Final Remarks

This review has examined the growing body of evidence supporting the efficacy of TCEs for pain management in patients with KOA. Current evidence supports that TCEs, including Tai Chi, Qigong, Baduanjin, Yijinjing, and Wuqinxi, promote pain control and improve physical function. The multifaceted benefits of TCEs extend beyond physical improvements, encompassing mental and emotional well-being, providing patients with sustainable methods for improving their quality of life.

While the evidence is compelling, further high-quality research, particularly randomized controlled trials, is warranted to explore the long-term effects of TCEs on KOA. Future studies should also focus on standardizing exercise protocols and tailoring interventions to individual patient needs and preferences.

TCEs represent a potentially valuable complementary therapy for KOA, bridging ancient wisdom with modern healthcare practices. By informing healthcare providers, institutions, and policymakers about the potential applications of TCEs, the integration of these practices into conventional clinical settings could improve the patient's quality of life.

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